

Swinburne University of Technology

Smart Art Project Business Report

July 2012

SWINBURNE DESIGN FACTORY

Executive Summary

In partnership with Colin McKinnon Dodd of the Mia Mia Gallery & Chairman of the Aboriginal Artists Development Fund (AADF) as well as Sharon Paton, CEO of The Koorie Heritage Trust, an interdisciplinary team of final year Swinburne University of Technology students have spent the past semester working in the Swinburne Design Factory on the Smart Art Project. Guided by Elizabeth Tunstall and Mark Tolson, the team of design, business, IT and anthropology students have worked ambitiously on a culturally sensitive project.

The Australian Aboriginal Art market has been growing at a considerable pace over the past two decades. In that time, it has attracted significant international attention with prices for some pieces reaching into the millions. Australian Aboriginal art is a culturally rich form of art, however much of the meaning and story behind the artwork goes untold, remaining in the piece and mind of its creator. The Smart Art project seeks to find a solution to this problem among many others including- the rampant exploitation of artists rights, unjust on sale royalty systems, authentication of artwork and the erosion of indigenous culture. The scope of the Swinburne Design Factory's Smart Art Project is enormous.

The methodologies used at the Design Factory were vast. Secondary research via journal articles and reports were undertaken and analysed in order to create a *visual annotative bibliography*. Primary research in the form of stakeholder interviews with indigenous community, gallery, art centre and artist were conducted in order to give a precise cultural and market based knowledge foundation to the team. *Affinity diagramming* was used to collate the team's ideas and we then moved on to *scenario building* and mapping in order to design and understand the user journey. A business model canvas was used to map out business details such as customer segments, value propositions and potential revenue sources. As the semester went on, holistic solution brainstorming was used to define three potential solutions and affable business models, presented at a final presentation and within this report.

One thing was clear about all solutions; the database or knowledge management system that provides storage of captured data and is accessible to the user via front end platforms, will be an integral part of all proposed solutions.

The first, solution 3D, is blue sky thinking- holograms, 3D images, and the invention of new mediums for capture. This solution would focus on digital recreations of story to provide authentication and an incredible user experience. This would require significant technological, business and operational innovation and would require the development of new technologies via partnerships with large scale technology firms.

Solution 2D includes the bundling of advanced yet current technologies into a capture suitcase for the community art centre and artists. The capture technology suitcase would include FLAC audio recording and haptic touch feedback sensory to capture the story and art making process. A near field communication (NFC) enabled canvas would allow access to captured data by the consumer, presumably via smart phone application.

Solution 1D is the quickest and easiest to market solution. It also includes the bundling of current and easily accessible and low-cost technologies such as video cameras and smart phones paired with a custom-built application to be used at the capture stage. After embedding the capture and story data within the art, radio frequency identification (RFID) and GPS enabled canvases provide authentication when paired with a ubiquitous smart phone application for consumer access.

On the business model side, we have identified that the main customer segment should be the community art centres as they are profoundly important link as they already have well established links with indigenous artists and communities and will also be able to aid in driving the Smart Art system. A subscription model to the holistic Smart Art system that is volume and product feature dependant was defined a key revenue source and is desirable. The business models should be platform based whereby it is necessary and advantageous to create a tight integration and reinforcing synergy between all three aspects; hardware, software and content.

Risks for each of the solutions were found. The nature and pace of technological change means that any implementable technologies may soon be redundant, requiring continuous research and development. Unproven technologies may reduce take up and technologies that are owned by external parties and are non-proprietary may limit controlling stake.

The Swinburne Design Factory team and partners are heading in the right direction in making a significant and beneficial change within this industry. With some further solutions based research and evaluation, it is our belief that the Smart Art project will have profound impact on the indigenous art market- improving transparency, limiting exploitation, sharing untold stories and most importantly helping artists and their communities.

Contents

Introduction	5
Current Landscape	6
Secondary Research Analysis	6
Environmental Analysis	7
Methodologies	14
Key Findings	15
Solutions	18
Solution 3D	19
Solution 2D	21
Solution 1D	23
Conclusion	24
Appendix A- Methodologies	25
Appendix B- Primary Research	38
References	43

Introduction

The two key objectives of this Smart Art Project came posed in question form with one question assigned to each of the two teams, they were as follows:

Communities Team: How do you capture the making of the art as both the visuals and the story?

Galleries Team: How do you embed/store the story within the artwork itself and how would the appropriate people access the story?

Although these two questions appeared to be somewhat simple in their written format when the actual tasks surrounding them were deconstructed the complexities began to surface. Going against the outline recommendation of splitting into two separate groups, it was decided that for the initial research stage the group would remain as one in order to build a shared level and basic understanding of the Aboriginal culture and the artwork produced by its people. As the research was conducted the problems, limits and boundaries of this difficult task were realised and there was a definite sense of confusion about where to start.

For a simplified and holistic understanding of the task at hand the group decided to create a well-defined purpose statement that read *'to design technology that can authenticate and validate artwork, embed story and facilitate on-sale royalties'*.

Current Landscape

The Aboriginal Australian Art market is one of the fastest growing sectors of the art market in terms of price and turnover. (Taylor, D & Coleman, L 2011). The last decade has seen prices and popularity of Australian Aboriginal artwork soar. This has been aided by big hits such as Clifford Possum Tjapaltjarri's Warlugulong which sold for \$2 million in 2007. Since the onset of the Global Financial Crisis and credit crunch in 2008 however, the art market as a whole has suffered. This has impacted the Aboriginal art market and according to the Australian Art Sales Digest, the value of Australian Aboriginal art sold at auction declined again in 2011 to \$8.2 million which was well below the record total set in 2007 at \$26.4 million (Furphy, J 2012). That being said, Colin McKinnon Dodd suggests the approximate value of the entire Australian Aboriginal Art market to be around \$300 million at present.

Customer buying behaviour is considerably different across this market. Many purchases are made from a personal investment perspective and according to Taylor and Coleman 2011, Aboriginal Art is considered to be an alternative asset class with approximate annual return of 6.6%. Apart from an investment perspective, the other side of the market is ownership by those that purchase for the aesthetics of a piece, their interest in art, and a myriad of other personal reasons. The Australian tourism industry is of great importance to the art market, and many tourists are purchasing Aboriginal art as a souvenir of their trip down under. Some key price determinants for Aboriginal art pieces sold at auction and galleries include the medium used, size of the piece, artist's popularity, whether the artist is deceased or not, time of the year sold and more. We envisage that a Smart Art system that captures, embeds and distributes the story behind the art piece with functionality of passing on sale royalties would become another value adding price determinant into the future.

Secondary Research Analysis

This analysis approach has been adopted from a traditional marketing macro-environment analysis tool. For the purpose of this report it is being used to outline the key findings from secondary research. Table 1 presents the findings of the environmental analysis.

Table 1. Environmental Analysis

ENVIRONMENTAL FACTOR	TREND/EVENT	DIRECTION	EXPLANATION	IMPLICATION
Political/Legal	Lack of strict laws and regulation (Rothwell 2010)	Threat ↓	This is a situation that unfortunately applies to the entire art market. It is slowly improving with time.	The art market is fraught with dishonest people, low quality or fraudulent artworks and the process of prosecution is very tiresome. This has created an environment where both sellers and buyers need to be weary
Political/Legal	Unregulated Industry (Acker 2008)	Threat ↔	The Aboriginal art market falls victim and suffers from some of the worst implications that can arise from an industry lacking regulation	Winikoff (2008) states that it is “an industry that currently operates in a feral and unregulated environment” where corruption and exploitation run wild. There are “disturbing levels of unethical, unscrupulous and illegal practice in the Aboriginal art industry”
Political/Legal	Industry push for increased regulation (Rothwell 2010)	Neutral ↔	The Aboriginal art market demands increased regulation and accountability within the market. This leads to the introduction of the Aboriginal Art Code in 2007	Government did not commit enough financial resources to achieve a well-established implementation of the Code. The Code when used in accordance with the ethical standards outlined is efficient but there are many who claim to follow the Code and don't. Some argue the market is improved while others make claims that it is worse off

Political/Legal	Minimal enforceable laws (Ayres 2007)	Threat ↓	Legal conflicts often avoid criminal prosecution	Many cases end up in court as civil matters and this leads to complete lack of accountability and creates no incentive for those involved to follow correct and ethical guidelines/laws
Legal	Intellectual Property regarding Aboriginal Art (Christie 2007)	Neutral ↔	The complexities associated when it comes to indigenous art and database storage	This affects the classifications of what can be considered IP and legal/cultural boundary issues as to what information can and should be stored and shared
Economic	Ground-breaking Sales (Taylor & Coleman, 2011)	Opportunity ↑	2007 saw the highest price ever recorded for an Aboriginal artwork (Clifford Possum, \$2m)	This was the first Aboriginal artwork to sell for over \$1m. This injected hope and also incentives for artists to reach this kind of calibre and status, it reinvigorated a focus on quality pieces
Economic	Global Financial Crisis (Rothwell 2010)	Threat ↑	Indigenous art market's bubble bursts between 2007 (\$24m) and 2008 (\$11.7m)	General concern that the aboriginal art market will never bounce back to the same as it was before the global financial crisis hit
Economic	Supply & Demand (O'Connel 2010)	Threat ↑	Popularity of indigenous artwork lead to mass production and fuelled exploitation	Over Supply of artwork had an impact on price and quality. A flood of poorly created artworks and collaborations brought uncertainty and effected credibility of genuine and authentic works
Economic	Global Financial Crisis (ABS 2010)	Threat ↑	Consumers tighten their spending budgets therefore spending less on luxury items	Entire art market suffers as a result of reduced spending. Bargain hunting and cheaper purchases fuel already existing problems with exploitation

Economic	Alternative Source of Investment (Battersby, 2010)	Threat ↓	Claims that up to 60% of aboriginal art is bought through self-managed super funds and acts as an investment for the owner	A great thing for the Aboriginal art market however new government legislation could ban the use of art, wine, collectables etc. from use within super funds and may ultimately impact the indigenous art market.
Economic	60/40 Split between gallery & artist (Kim 2011)	Neutral ↔	This arrangement is standard for the entire art market not just Aboriginal art	60/40 split gives the gallery a vested interest to promote the artist and sell their paintings. 40/60 used to be a common occurrence but galleries would also charge a fee on top as well. There are also strong arguments for 50/50
Economic	Employment	Opportunity ↑	The Aboriginal Art market is providing increased employment	Employment opportunities are growing in rural areas not just for Aboriginal artists but also for the systems and support mechanisms around them, e.g. Art Centres, Aboriginal galleries
Economic	Art Valuations (Taylor & Coleman, 2011)	Neutral ↔	Valuations can be statistically measured based on any number of price determinants including; the artist, the gallery/ auction house, where it was made, its age.	This can encourage some artists to strive for quality instead of falling victim to the mentality of the times where more is better. Quality pieces are more likely to reach better and more well-respected avenues of sale and where an artist's work is exhibited says a lot about its calibre
Economic	Deceased artist sales (Taylor & Coleman, 2011)	Opportunity ↑	On average a piece of Aboriginal artwork is worth 12% more if the artist is deceased. Increased value after an artist dies is common place in the entire art market.	This may encourage support for On Sale Royalties as many artists would like their families to keep on benefiting after they have passed away. A better system for On Sale Royalties will ultimately help with issues of regulation as well

Economic	Offshore Production (Altman, 2002; Golvan 1992; Simons 2000)	Threat	↑	Aboriginal 'style' artworks are being produced offshore by non-indigenous people/companies	This artwork labelled 'Aboriginal Style' fool some uneducated buyers, breach 'Fair Trade' and are used by some Australian businesses for the tourist market
Technological	Digital Revolution (Lehn et al. 2009)	Opportunity	↑	There can be no denying that the world is in the midst of a digital revolution that appears to have no bounds	Galleries and museums are having to employ new visually exciting and interactive technologies to attract visitors and keep up with a rapidly changing environment
Technological/ Socio-Cultural	Internet Communications (Nathan 2005)	Opportunity	↑	Communication enhanced by the internet in rural areas	The internet has increased internal communications for rural communities as well as external communications with mainstream society. This also aids indigenous business and artists
Technological/ Socio-Cultural	Future education using modern technology (Verran & Christie 2007)	Opportunity	↑	Using DVD recordings to capture stories for future generations both internal and external to the communities, E.g. Yolgnu people	The importance of story preservation has been realised as has the ease and longevity of adopting new technologies to aid this process
Technological/ Socio-Cultural	Community Radio Stations (Buchtman 2000)	Opportunity	↑	Remote communities embrace the radio. It is a widely accepted means of communication	This allows unity, inclusion and customisation. There are many indigenous run community radio stations in remote and rural areas. Focus is on indigenous people and indigenous issues
Technological/ Socio-Cultural	Technology adding value (Taylor 2011)	Opportunity	↑	Traditional media has reputation-affirming traits and has a significant impact on price determinants of Aboriginal artwork	Media is giving exposure to Aboriginal art and helping to promote individual artists. It is helping the spread by word of mouth and to build momentum for up and coming artists/established artists and their exhibitions.

Socio-Cultural	Original Intent of artwork (Sharifan 2010)	Threat ↑	The original purpose and intent of Aboriginal paintings was to convey their 'dreaming'	As external influences from the modern world take hold, both cultural and financial, the true essence of the art is being overlooked and sometimes completely lost. Large implications for the passing on of story to future generations
Socio-Cultural	Business activities between Aboriginal and settler communities (Foley 2010)	Opportunity ↑	Increased understanding and stronger relationships between Aboriginal and settler communities is important for future business prosperity	Aboriginal business activities are greatly dependent on the degree of mutual socio-cultural understanding between the aboriginal community and the settler community. With mutual respect and understanding more compromise in a business sense will be possible and less compromise in a cultural sense will be achievable
Socio-Cultural	Ethical Consumerism	Opportunity ↑	Society as a whole is becoming more conscientious about what they buy and whether it has been produced in an ethically sound manner	Promotion of 'ethical Aboriginal art' that is produced without exploitation will ensure buyer confidence as well as higher quality artworks. Possibility of likening art produced via means of exploitation to that of blood diamonds
Socio-Cultural	Modernity (Connolly 2001)	Neutral ↔	Aboriginals who embrace modern culture are sometimes viewed as less authentic	A clash of traditional culture and modern-day culture is very apparent especially for the younger generations. They are sometimes viewed by their own culture as being not true to their aboriginality. This creates internal conflict and is a hard-balancing act for many young Aboriginals
Socio-Cultural	Consumer Uncertainty (Rothwell 2010)	Threat ↑	Buyers of Aboriginal art become weary and lack confidence to purchase because of market conditions	A direct effect on the market because from exploitation, mass production, fraudulent pieces and collaborations. Detrimental to the entire market and damages trust and authenticity

Socio-Cultural	Exploitation	Threat	↑	Unethical treatment of artists and unethical business deals driven by a dirty dollar	Increased with market demand with the effect of decreasing overall value and promoting unethical treatment of artists, also leading to over supply
Socio-Cultural	Education for a sustainable future (Wilson 2010)	Threat	↓	Original techniques and methods for producing Aboriginal art are 'dying with the desert masters'	Proper teachings and passing on of story will enable this art form to stay alive. Education within the communities by their older members is the key, as well as using new technologies to 'capture' the process and stories behind the pieces
Socio-Cultural	Commodification (Seabrook 2004)	Threat	↑	Aboriginal art being treated as a commodity	Aboriginal art is a precious thing and in its truly authentic state it is rich with culture and story. The commodification of this art form is robbing it of the elements that make it truly special
Socio-Cultural	Songlines Project (Rintoul 2012)	Threat	↑	Project to capture two of the most important Western Desert stories; the Giant Perentie Lizard and the Seven Sisters Dreaming. Traditional Anunga men feel project's recordings are too intrusive to "sacred men's law"	"Traditional Anangu men are inseparable from their law and believe their very existence is being degraded and passed off as a common art form". There is a large amount of conflict surrounding this project and its ethicality. "Aboriginal people are on the back foot for our intellectual copyright" the article quoted (Mr Lester)
Technological	Technologically advanced materials (Thakur 2010)	Opportunity	↑	Advanced material such as acrylic paints and canvases are adopted by Aboriginal artists	Adopting modern materials brings longevity to artwork and this opens up opportunity for artists and increases their ability to compete within the broader market
Technological	Advancements in communication	Opportunity	↑	Increased accessibility of internet and telephones	Opens up the lines of communication between rural artists and urban galleries for better business relationships to be built
Technological	Texts Audio Moving	Opportunity	↑	Elders want to create a database	With elders being more accepting of capturing

Cultural/ Environment	Images (Verran et al. 2007)	for the younger generations so they can access and learn about their own heritage.	story through modern technology the possibilities are endless. TAMI is just one of many possible approaches to such a process and solution
	Increased mining Threat and associated personnel (Turk 2003) ↑	Land is being used for mining purposes and is creating a clash of cultural values	Native land is subject to mining and also creating a clash of western modernity and native indigenous tradition

The secondary research outlined in the above table was compiled from research gathered for the individual Visual Annotated Bibliographies. Since then more in-depth analyses have been completed to understand specific technologies that can possibly be used in the capturing, sharing and embedding of story stages. Other general research and reading was also undertaken individually to extend knowledge regarding the cultural issues surrounding this project.

Methodologies

After the secondary research was completed, *primary research* in the form of client fields trips, (Mia Mia Gallery and Koorie Heritage Trust) as well as face to face interviews were undertaken to ascertain what stakeholders, particularly artists, art centre coordinators and gallery owners, required and desired from a Smart Art product and how they currently interacted within the art market. Appendix A outlines the questions used by interviewers. Appendix B provides a brief summary of each interview.

Information received from the research stage was collated through the *affinity diagramming* method. Further questions to be answered by the team were made clear in this process and set the stage for *scenario mapping*. Scenario Mapping provided an in depth understanding of the user experience and generated discussion around how stakeholders would interact with various aspects of the business model, such as revenue and key activities. Scenarios were developed by imagining key stakeholders' interactions with the technology at various stages.

An extensive business model brainstorm session with the use of a *business model canvas* provided key insights into business model considerations such as revenue streams, cost drivers and primary activities. This activity particularly generated discussion and decision around the key customer of Smart Art Technologies.

See Appendix A for an in depth look at the methodologies.

Key Findings

After primary and secondary research, a *process flow* for the interaction with the technology was developed and 5 main stages were identified.

The Artist & Community

Artists and their surrounding community are the inspiration for artwork. Each story is created within a local context and may be influenced by thousands of years of tradition and culture. Smart Art technology and business models must work within this culture, be community led and support the desires of the community.

Capture

Capturing the story may require the use of yet undeveloped technology or the assistance of trained, local professionals. Our primary customer, the Art Centre or Artist Firm, primarily operates within this stage; marketing the technology to potential artists, selling, leasing, hiring or loaning the use of the capture technology and facilitating legal and ethical procedures.

Embed

Depending on the technology used, embedding the data with the artwork may require developed technology sold as a resource to the customer. Professionals may also be required to assist in editing the information ready for the end user. At the end of this stage, the data is ready to be accessed by an end user through a technology attached to the artwork.

Point of Sale

The artwork, embedding with the SmartArt technology, is distributed through the current art system, including galleries and museums for on sale to private and public users.

User

End users are defined as people who 'consume' the artwork and correlated Smart Art data. This includes public consumers in museums as well as private buyers with privileged access from their homes. Business model activities in the final two stages primarily consist of facilitating access to the data and providing education for users in order to generate demand.

It was determined that the key customer segment of the Smart Art technology should be the Aboriginal Art Centre/Artist's Firm. They were selected due to the fact that they have:

- the resources to procure access to the technology
- connections with artists who would utilize the technology for distribution on the market
- motivation and incentive to utilize and drive the adoption of the Smart Art technology
- ethical standing within the indigenous community

Key stakeholders identified to be interacting with the technology include:

- Rural& Rural Artists
- Smart Art Representative
- Art Centre/ Artist's Firm (customer)
- KMS- Smart Art Technologies Pty Ltd.
- Gallery Owner
- Private Consumer
- Public Consumer

Through the research it became apparent that a timeless, non-changing storage solution for the captured information would need to be developed. This solution ties all the components of the project together across all stakeholders and maintains the data for generations (regardless of changing technologies.) This 'storage facility and access platform' has been termed 'The Database' and is a key component to each solution presented.

Features of the database could include:

Information Archive

The database is essentially an archive of all the information captured through Smart Art Technologies. This information would need to be stored in a way that it is protected, accessible by the right people and does not expire.

Website/app/digital interface

The data above would be accessed and interacted with via an online portal. This could be a website, an application or other technology developed in the future. The digital interface would need to allow easy access to information in a protected way.

User Profile

User profiles, similar to Facebook, which allow users to control which other users have access to what information, would be an ideal way to control privacy and access concerns and maintain the locus of control within the Community.

Two-sided Marketplace

A two-sided marketplace, similar to eBay, could be created for the buying and selling of Smart Art. This would generate demand for Smart Art technologies and connect buyers directly to sellers, as well as allowing authorized sign off for any transactions.

e-Commerce Facilities

Conducting transactions over the internet means that resale royalties could be automatically attributed to the appropriate account.

Multi-tiered System

The most important aspect of the database in the multi-tiered system, allowing certain privileges to authorized people and a high degree of customization as to who can access what and when.

Overall Considerations for the Design Factory team on the Smart Art project were that the project has to be; artist-led and controlled to avoid exploitation, useable and accessible to all stakeholders, innovative and be able to promote sustainable and ethical practices

Solutions

Derived from extensive primary and secondary research conducted, group brainstorming, analysis and evaluation; three final solutions have been formulated. Each has been carefully and thoughtfully designed, encompassing components that function harmoniously together to form an integrated product and service offering. A general platform business model has been applied, in which the integration and synergy between the hardware, software and content strengthens the holistic solution. These proposed solutions also consider the technologies currently available and projected to be available in the future. For this reason, each solution can be seen to build on the last, over a time span of 20 years.

Each of the solutions will begin with an overview of the solution and will then move onto the workings of the solution's business model, highlighting the value propositions, potential revenue streams, cost drivers and key risks involved among many other things. As many of the integral components of the business model remain consistent across the three solutions, after the first solution's business model is presented in depth, only *key differences* between the models will subsequently be highlighted to avoid repetition. Three viable solutions are presented below for the development in the Smart Art System ; 3D, 2D and 1D.

Solution - 3D

This offering attempts to look outside the current Aboriginal art making formats and provide an option that connects the artist to their original culture and forms being used. The core concept of this solution relies on the development of a portable motion sensor technology that has the capability to capture an artist and his/her movement visually and audibly as they carry out the art making process. This will then allow a 3D image to be captured and presented in any form that is desired by the end consumer. Artists will then not be limited to the current art forms and materials but will have the capability to draw in the sand or on rock and still capture the complete image. This could then be transposed in the form of a hologram projection which could be accompanied by a 3D printed canvas image where viewers could activate the painting and witness an artist painting and telling the story of their art simultaneously as if they were right in front of them. Authentication capabilities for this technology would be embedded into the technology and allow for the analysis of the artwork through biometric scanning technology. This solution is anticipated to take the longest to develop, as it is dependent on the development of technology that does not currently exist. For this reason, a partnership would have to be formed with a company such as Microsoft to provide the necessary skills and expertise.

Business Model

The business model for this solution is based around our main *customer segment*; the community art center which also includes galleries where artists create. The community art centers have been selected as our main customer segment as they have well established links with artists, and will be an essential location for artist access to the technologies. There is also the distinct possibility of direct sales of the system to the artists; thereby it is worth noting their potential as a key customer segment.

Some of the *value propositions* that our offering provides our customer segment include the ability to create higher and new revenue streams, increased exposure in the domestic and international market, the satisfaction of enabling ethical and fair operations within the market, helping to aid in maintaining and passing on indigenous culture and much more. *Customer relationships* will be managed mainly via the Smart Art System platform itself, but also in various other forms such as through social media, email, phone calls, and through direct contact and interpersonal communication at the community art centers. The physical product will be delivered via existing logistical distribution *channels* whilst the service is digitally delivered.

Several *revenue sources* identified include the sale or potential lease of capture technology such as the motion sensor tech to the community art center and potentially direct to artists as well. KMS could create a subscription model that would be volume and product feature dependent, one that also provides access and use of the entire platform (website, app and database). On the digital platform side, an artists/art centre/artwork advertising mechanism could be an alternate revenue source. Brokerage fees from art sold on the platform are likely, and it is recommended that a structured commission/ on sale royalty model be created. If successfully integrated into the platform KMS would obtain revenue via sales and resale of artwork. Depending upon final mediums used for the consumer access to the artwork and story (holograms, 3D printing etc.) there are various monetization possibilities. Partnerships with technology providers and payments for platform use on an impression basis come to mind. There is also a possibility of government subsidies and funding providing alternate revenue streams.

Cost Drivers for this solution include the capture kit motion sensing technology procurement from manufacturers either via outright purchase or potentially licensing for our own manufacture if KMS were to become an OEM. KMS platform/ database development and ongoing maintenance will be on going. The training and wages of direct sales representatives for the system as well as ongoing research & development into technologies and platform would be a considerable cost, as will KMS operational staff wages.

Key Partners would include the community art centers, members of KMS, manufacturers of capture technology, the government if they are subsidizing and or driving the smart art system, and several digital technology providers. KMS' operational part for this solution requires several *key activities*. The management and operation of the entire platform including the database and customer centric front-end platform is essential. The direct sales of subscription packages including the capture technology by our agents and subsequent training and education on the system is also necessary. Active marketing and other operational activities will become clearer further into the product development cycle. In order to operate and provide the product and service offering to our customer segment, KMS will require a number of physical, capital and human resources. Some of these identified *key resources* include; KMS staff, office space, R&D location, computers, smart phones, internet access and bandwidth.

Several possible *risks* have been identified. The development and implementation of this solution is partnership dependant and would most likely not be utilizing proprietary KMS owned technologies. Said technologies are visionary, perhaps distant and not yet market proven. The case for true innovation is stronger due to this; however as with anything new there may be market resistance on the implementation side. The requirement of digital rights management software and systems is increasingly higher.

Solution - 2D

This solution embodies two mechanisms that have been designed to provide the artist with a more customisable experience, suited to their requirements and needs. The first is an immobile set up which would be stationary within a shared space, presumably within an art centre. The set up would consist of technologies such as a haptic sensor mats, FLAC recording and adapted inkling technology. The second would provide an option of a mobile suitcase with technologies including adapted inkling technology, camera and microphone.

In addition, artists could authenticate the artwork by using either authenticating ink, canvases with embedded thread or NFC technology. Although the complete raw recorded audio and visuals would be kept, it would also be edited into a format and timeframe more suitable for the end-user. The story behind an artwork could then also be shared using NFC technology through their smart phone or tablet that would then link to the information on the database.

The database in this instance could take form as a two-sided market place where artwork could also be sold. This would provide the opportunity to also facilitate the transfer of on sale royalties. The underlining concept guiding this solution is that the artist would be able to customise the experience to suit their desired needs and requirements.

Business Model.

Many features of the business model such as the value propositions, customer relationships, channels, key activities and key resources remain similar to solution 3D. However, there are several distinct differences, highlighted below.

Revenue sources can include the physical asset sale of the NFC enabled canvas direct to the community art centers, which could be built into a holistic Smart Art System subscription package. On the consumer side, a KMS Smart Art App could be based on the freemium model whereby a free/lite version is created and subsidized with advertising. A full version of the KMS Smart Art App would be a paid version that provides full access and ownership capability, and the pricing of said App would be market and product feature driven.

Cost Drivers for this solution will also include the capture kit technology procurement from providers either via outright purchase or licensing. KMS Smart Art App development and ongoing maintenance would be essential in combination with existing database development and maintenance. For the KMS Smart Art App, KMS would encounter digital payment processing fees, and payments of commission to app store platform operators.

Key Partners would also include manufacturers of capture suitcase technology and manufacturers of the NFC enabled canvas, along with previously mentioned partners.

Some possible *risks* have been identified. The initial capital outlay and expenditure for the capture kit by the customer may be off putting and reduce initial take up. This however could be mitigated via implementation of a subscription package including the capture kit and reducing the initial capital outlay.

Solution - 1D

The final solution has been devised using straightforward elements which are actionable within a short time frame allowing the technology to be developed approximately within a 6-12-month timeframe. For this solution, the main technology facilitating the capturing of story, embedding process and authentication of artwork is an online application compatible with all smart phones and tablets. An artist would download the application to facilitate the capturing of his/her art making. The artist would be prompted through the process by the application and the information and recordings would then be uploaded onto the database into the assigned areas. The purchasers of the artwork would then use picture recognition technology to connect to the database of information. This would also provide further authentication of the artwork, as more people would confirm the current location of the original via GPS. The artwork would be authenticated using RFID stickers with anti-tamper technology that would be placed on the back of each artwork. RFID stickers do have a limited lifespan so they would need to be updated at a later stage and potentially replaced with a more durable technology solution.

Business Model.

Many features of the business model such as the value propositions, customer relationships, channels, key activities and key resources remain similar to solution 3D. However, there are several distinct differences, highlighted below.

Extra *Revenue sources* identified include the sale of the KMS Smart Art Capture application to the community art center and directly to artists. KMS could once again create a subscription model that would be volume (canvas) and product feature dependent, one that also provides access and use of the entire platform (website, app and database). Within this subscription package, the physical asset sales of the RFID enabled canvas should be built in tiered pricing levels.

Cost Drivers for this solution include the RFID tag procurement from supplier either via purchase or licensing, KMS Consumer App development and ongoing maintenance, as well as database development and maintenance are all paramount in this solution. *Key Partners* would include manufacturers of the RFID tags and App store partners such as Microsoft, Google or Apple. Some of the *risks* identified in this at present, RFID technology have not been developed by the Smart Art team and therefore the technology is owned by external interests which may reduce control to a certain degree, and is likely to become redundant after 5-10 years. As the capture system is currently defined, there may also be problems in the capture data lacking uniformity across the board resulting in an inconsistent user experience.

Conclusion

Throughout the semester the interdisciplinary team at Swinburne Design Factory attempted to answer the question of how *'to design technology that can authenticate and validate artwork, embed story and facilitate on-sale royalties'*. The process undertaken by the team was defined by the methodologies such as primary & secondary research, affinity brainstorming, scenario mapping and business model mapping. These tools were used in depth and ultimately enabled the creation of three theoretical and plausible solutions- 3D, 2D & 1D.

What remains consistent across all three solutions is the idea and necessity of a database to enable the capturing, embedding and viewing of the story behind an artwork. Targeting the community art centres as the key customer segment is also viewed as a requirement. It is apparent that whichever solution is pursued, for it to gain significant traction in the indigenous community and art market it has to be indigenous led; it must reduce exploitation, be easy to use, and be an innovative / sustainable solution.

The three solutions presented in this report are all in their respective infancies. Significant further detailed research and analysis is required around the intimate product features, technological boundaries, user experience journeys and business model intricacies. Business model solutions and technological product features differ between the three presented solutions; however, it can be justly stated that all three would enable the primary outcomes such as reduction in exploitation, improvement in authentication, passing of the story and fair on sale royalties to be adequately met.

Though we have but just taken the first steps towards developing such a solution, it is our belief that it is very attainable and that *the journey is the reward*.

Appendix A- Methodologies.

1) Primary Research- Interviews

- **The Alcaston Gallery**
'Mainstream Gallery'
Beverly Knight
Brunswick St, FITZROY VIC
- **East Gippsland Aboriginal Arts Corporation (EGAAC)**
'Indigenous Art Centre'
Bianca Baker/ Lee Derrick & Artists
Bairnsdale, GIPPSLAND VIC
- **Muk Muk Gallery**
'Aboriginal art Wholesaler'
Mike Mitchell
Alice Springs, NT

Activity Purpose:

To interview and gather information and feedback from businesses and artists who have direct links to the industry.

Objectives:

To gain external opinions and perspectives to help provide a more rounded outlook that was outside the realm of the information provided by our clients and the secondary research gathered by ourselves.

Findings/Results:

External insight from market players who were not directly linked to the project helped us to paint the bigger picture. See Appendix B for more in-depth analysis of interviews.

2) Primary Research- Artist Interview Questions

Interview and Exercise Guide

I. About You

Purpose: To warm up the participant, get them comfortable and open. To gather information to help interpret his or her responses.

Instructions: Engage the participant in a conversation addressing the following questions.

NOTE: You don't have to ask them all, just note whether or not they are covered in the conversation. Keep the questions open ended, but also be mindful of the time and gently lead them to the next question when they stray too far.

1. Who are you and where are you from? (Allow the most time for this one.)
2. Describe your family relations. How do you support and sustain them?
3. What are some activities that you like to do? With whom do you do these activities?
4. Tell us the story of what you did this past Saturday:
5. Tell us the story of what you did yesterday:
6. What is most important to you in life?
7. What keeps you awake at night?
8. What provides you with comfort?

II. About Aboriginal Cultural Values

Purpose: Understand people's cultural value systems and how they guide their life and their work.

Instructions: Ask the participant to give you a tour of their home, office, or outdoor area. Notice the environment. Ask them to select 8-10 things in the environment that best convey who they are as an Aboriginal person. Ask permission to photograph those items.

Questions to ask about what they think are the cultural values of their people:

1. You are of the _____ peoples. Would you tell me a story that best describes what you consider to be the characteristics of the _____?
2. What are ways of thinking, doing, and being that are important for the _____ to pass onto future generations?

3. How are those ways different from previous generations? How are they similar?
4. How would you expect those ways to be different for your great grandchildren?
5. How are those ways reflected in everyday life for you, your family, and your community? How are they reflected in ceremony?
6. What are the strengths and weaknesses of those ways?
7. What are the threats to them and what opportunities exist to sustain them?
8. What makes the ways of the _____ peoples different from those of surrounding Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities? Other Indigenous peoples? Other non-indigenous peoples?

Questions to ask about what they think are the cultural values of their people as related to the Art market:

1. How does the ways of thinking, doing, and being of the _____ peoples affect your art making and/or promoting and selling?
2. Ask them to show you a piece of art work. Tell me the story of how you created/promoted/sold this art work.
3. How did the process of creating/promoting/selling this art work compare to others?
4. What are the strengths and weaknesses of these processes?
5. What are the biggest threats to your work and business? What do they cost you? Your family? Your community?
6. What are some of the major opportunities in the art market that you have not been able to take advantage of? Why not? What does this cost you? Your family? Your community?
- 7.

Questions to ask about what they think are the cultural values of other people in the art market:

1. In the art market, who are the kinds of people that you typically meet? Would you tell me a story that best describes what you consider to be the characteristics of these people?
2. What do you believe are the ways of thinking, doing, and being that are important for them to pass onto future generations?
3. How are those ways different from previous generations? How are they similar?
4. How would you expect those ways affect your great grandchildren?
5. What are the strengths and weaknesses of those ways?
6. What are the threats to them and what opportunities exist to sustain them?
7. What makes the ways of these peoples different from the ways of your people?

III. About Innovation

Purpose: To understand how people define innovation as well as do it.

Questions to ask about what they think about innovation.

1. Governments and businesses like to talk about innovation. In your own words, how would you define the word innovation? Is there an Aboriginal word for this? If yes, what is it?
2. Tell me a story that best describes your definition of innovation.
3. What are ways in which your communities have been innovating?
4. What kinds of innovations do you see around you every day?
5. What are some innovations that you would like to bring to your communities? To the Aboriginal art market?
6. What would be required to make these innovations happen? What are the barriers?
7. Tell me a story of what the Aboriginal art market would be like in 50 years if those barriers did not exist.

IV. About Technologies in life, community, etc. - Card Sorting Exercise

Purpose: To understand how people use and classify technologies.

Instructions:

1. Write down on index cards all the technologies that exist in the environment (personal, work related, etc.)
2. Have the participant create an index card with the name of the participant, a male Elder in the community, a female Elder in the community, a young male in the community, a young female in the community.
3. Lay out the cards of technologies in a circle. Have the participant place each person in the centre of the circle of technologies and tell a story of how the person would use the different technologies surrounding them. Capture the results and comments in booklet.

V. About Technologies in Art Market - Card Sorting Exercise

Purpose: To understand how people use and classify technologies in the Aboriginal Art Market.

Instructions:

1. Add to the index cards all the technologies that exists in the environment (personal, work related, etc.) cards that list the types of technologies used in the art market, with descriptions. Have the participant add any other technologies they know of in the art market.
2. Have the participant create an index card with the name of the participant and the other people with whom they interact in the art market.
3. Lay out the cards of technologies in a circle. Have the participant place each person in the centre of the circle of technologies and tell a story of how the person would use the different technologies to support the Aboriginal art market surrounding them. Capture the results and comments in booklet.

Wrap Up

1. If there were three key take-aways from our discussion today, what would they be?
2. What are one or two things that I should know about you as a person?
3. Do you have any questions for me?

3) Primary Research- Gallery Interview Questions

I. About the Gallery

Purpose: To warm up the participant, get them comfortable and open. To gather information to help interpret his or her responses.

Instructions: Engage the participant in a conversation addressing the following questions. NOTE: You don't have to ask them all, just note whether are not they are covered in the conversation. Keep the questions open ended, but also be mindful of the time and gently lead them to the next question when they stray too far.

9. Who are you and where are you from? (Allow the most time for this one.)
10. What role do you play in the gallery?
11. What is the gallery's mission and history?
12. What are the strengths, weaknesses, threats, and opportunities in the Aboriginal Art market?
13. What is your business model? (Who are your partners, how do they make money, how do you segment your clients, how do you segment the artists)?
14. What roles do the State and/or Federal Government play in supporting the Aboriginal Art Market? How does that connect to your gallery?

About the Galleries Values and the Aboriginal Art Marketing and Selling Processes

Purpose: Understand the business of marketing and/or selling Aboriginal Art

Instructions: Ask the participant to give you a tour of the gallery. Notice the environment. Ask them to select 8-10 things in the environment that are crucial to marketing/selling Aboriginal Art.

Questions about what they think are the cultural values of their people:

1. What are your biggest challenges in marketing and selling art? Can you provide a story of the last piece of Aboriginal art that you sold successfully? Unsuccessfully? What factors are necessary for a successful sale?
2. What is the role of story or narrative in marketing Aboriginal art?
3. How do you communicate with investors and private collectors? Do they have any exclusive purchase options before that of the mainstream public?
4. Apart from private collectors and investors, what other types of people are buying aboriginal art? Are there any emerging markets of interest?
5. Who do you regard as your most valuable buyer markets?
6. What avenues do you use to promote the up-coming exhibitions?
7. What qualities and characteristics are buyers looking for when purchasing aboriginal art?

Questions about their relationships with artists/buyers

1. How would you describe your relationship with Aboriginal artists and their communities? Is it different from non-Aboriginal artists? How do you find artists? How do you build trust? What happens if trust is lost?
2. What are the most important links in the supply and distribution network? E.g. Is it artists/community art centre, gallery/ buyer, wholesaler/distributor, etc.?
3. If you were able to technically embed story within the artwork itself, what affect would it have on the artist/ buyer relationship? What impact do you think this could have on indigenous cultural awareness, repeat sales etc.?
4. What information do you give a buyer during purchase? What else do you give a buyer during purchase? Is there a standardised system for purchases?
5. What information do you keep about the buyer? Where/how is it stored?

Questions about Values of Aboriginal art

1. What are the key price determinants of indigenous art in your opinion? Who determines it and does it need to change in your opinion?
2. How much have you had to adjust sale prices under the economic conditions of the last four years?
3. How does the gallery determine how much commission they will receive from a piece of art work? Does it vary, is it negotiated, or is it set?
4. What percentage of the sale's money goes back to the artist? How does it get back to the artist?

Questions about Authentication

1. When selling artwork how do you make sure it's authentic?
2. What would your criteria be for success with the Aboriginal Smart Art project if we made it work? What would be the tangible forms of success? What would be things they would like people to say about the Gallery and the Aboriginal Smart Art project?
3. Are there any other things we should consider in giving you this successful outcome?
4. If this dream system was created what would inspire you and others in your position to use it?

Questions about Innovation

Purpose: To understand how people define innovation as well as do it.

Questions to ask about what they think about innovation.

8. Governments and businesses like to talk about innovation. In your own words, how would you define the word innovation? Tell me a story that best describes your definition of innovation.
9. What has been some significant innovations in the Aboriginal Art Market in last 10 years?
10. What are some areas that are in need of change in the Aboriginal Art Market? Is there anyone who is making those changes? How?
11. Which technologies does the gallery use or not use? Are any new or interactive technologies utilised? (Is a tour possible?)
12. Have you seen any technologies overseas that you think could be implemented here to enhance the gallery experience?

Questions about Technologies in Art Market - Card Sorting Exercise

Purpose: To understand how people use and classify technologies in the Aboriginal Art Market.

Instructions:

1. Create index cards all the technologies that exists in the environment (personal, work related, etc.) with descriptions. Have the participant add any other technologies they know of in the art market.

2. First have them sort based on technologies that they currently use:

A) to procure artwork from artists?

B) to manage assets and inventory?

C) to authenticate work?

D) to secure work from theft?

E) to communicate with potential buyers?

F) to track sales and royalties?

G) for any other parts of the process?

3. Next have them sort based on technologies that they would use in the future:

A) to procure artwork from artists?

B) to manage assets and inventory?

C) to authenticate work?

D) to secure work from theft?

E) to communicate with potential buyers?

F) to track sales and royalties?

G) for any other parts of the process?

VI. Wrap Up

4. If there were three key take-aways from our discussion today, what would they be?

5. What are one or two things that I should know about you as a person?

6. Do you have any questions for me?

Visual Annotated Bibliographies

Activity Definition:

Secondary research was conducted through Visual Annotated Bibliographies. This served the purpose of providing Literature Reviews and visual representations in a quadrant form with polar opposite axis to help identify the gaps that existed with our research. The activity was firstly undertaken individually before compiling all of the group's results into one big visual illustration.

Objectives:

- To identify the gaps that existed in our research so that specific research tasks may be delegated to fill them.
- To gain insight into the 'Big Picture' and current state of the market/s.

Findings/Results:

The main areas in need of further research were:

- International market conditions and technological developments
- Technological advancements both nationally and internationally
- Consumer insights, demands and willingness to pay
- Indigenous perspectives
- Existing legislation and regulation

Client Field Trips

- Koorie Heritage Trust
- Mia Mia Gallery

Activity Purpose: To give the project context and immerse ourselves in our client's place of business and environment.

Objectives: To gain perspective, broaden knowledge and obtain firsthand look at the situation through the eyes of our clients.

Findings/Results: The issues within the Aboriginal art market that our clients are trying to rectify are extremely complex. The current market has large problems with exploitation. There is a dire need for education of indigenous communities and artists as well as non-indigenous Australians (general public and private buyers).

Two main focuses were identified.

Mia Mia Gallery was focused on the capturing of story and its connection (embedding) to a physical artwork as a 'value add' to the private buyer and future generations both indigenous and non-indigenous.

The Koorie Heritage Trust was focused on the improved facilitation of On-Sale Royalties.

Affinity Brainstorming

Activity Definition:

The interactive process of creating an 'Immersive Project Area'. Affinity Brainstorming is an effective analysis tool used for inter-disciplinary projects that allows consideration and easy interpretation of all ideas. This is achieved by using colour coded post-it notes and placing them on a large wall at their best fit locations. They can then be rearranged and sorted as many times as they need and a clustering pattern can be observed.

Objectives:

To create a non-judgemental environment where all outputs, ideas and solutions may be considered without scrutiny. To enable us to immerse ourselves in the problem and see all potential avenues that may be worth pursuing. To identify common threads and to group and categorise similar outputs, ideas and solutions across the five identified stages being:

- Communities
- Capture
- Embed
- Point of Sale
- End Users

Findings/Results:

Identified core people, groups, themes, ideas and areas where thorough knowledge had been built. These similarities and common themes helped identify a focus to move forward with. It helped segment, prioritise and strengthen our approach and direction. Further identified key gaps in knowledge and areas that needed to be addressed and researched in more detail. A main one was the actual technologies that could be used in solutions. Reclassification and a heightened level of understanding regarding the end users involved and what was a feasible outcome for both a public and private end user.

Business Model Mapping

Activity Definition:

The purpose of this mapping process is to create a Business Model Canvas which is '*a shared language for describing, visualizing, assessing and changing business models*'. This is achieved through a group effort of brainstorming (and using post-it notes) to create a visual representation of key stages of business activity and their interactions with one another. Basically '*a business model describes the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers and captures value*'.

Objectives:

To create a blueprint of how 9 key stages of the business are going to interact with each other. The 9 Key Stages of the Business Model are:

- Key Activities
- Key Partners
- Key Resources
- Value Propositions
- Channels
- Cost Structure
- Revenue Streams

Findings/Results:

Consumers for the project's consideration were not actually the end users but the internal customers for 'KMS' (Koorie Heritage Trust, Mia Mia Gallery and Swinburne Design Factory), these were; Art Centres, Artist Firms and Private and Public Galleries. The traditional business model approach was useful to a certain point but it then needed to be adapted and remodelled itself into one that was more suited for this project.

Idea Cards

Activity Definition:

This activity was for open reign ideation both practical and blue sky ideas were welcome. This task was achieved by everyone sketching out individual ideas onto an 'idea card'.

Objectives:

To consider every idea within every stage so that no leaf went unturned. To evaluate the ideas in terms of:

- Value to; Artist, Community and Buyer
- Level of Investment; Existing, Customise or Create
- Infrastructure and Technology

Findings/Results:

As this was an individual exercise that was then brought together and analysed as a whole the ideas that repeated themselves, sketched by many of the group members, were the ones that had the best chance of going the distance. Common themes and similar ideas were identified and these were put aside and developed into stronger ideas with a heightened level of customisation.

Scenario Building Activity

Activity Definition:

This involved building real life scenarios that were a step by step representation of what would occur within every separate idea scenario. The process was completed by sketching and writing rough notes on A3 scenario maps that provided 5 steps.

Objectives:

To evaluate the ideas and individual scenarios put forth and rate their merit for achieving the project's core objectives.

Findings/Results:

Doing this highlighted the strengths and pitfalls of the ideas when they were put into real life user scenarios. This helped to eliminate problematic approaches and focus our efforts on the scenarios that proved to be the most user friendly and beneficial to all stakeholders.

Appendix B- Primary Research

The Alcaston Gallery Interview Summary – Amanda Williams

This interview was conducted with Beverly Knight on Thursday 19th April at the Alcaston Gallery (11 Brunswick Street, Fitzroy Melbourne). Beverly Knight is a non-indigenous gallery owner who established the Alcaston Gallery in 1989 after what she called “a persistent request from the community and the Central Australian Aboriginal Media Association (CAAMA) to do so”. She has close connections are to CAAMA (situated in Alice Springs) and indigenous people from Arnhem Land and when she opened the gallery in 1989 there were only two other galleries showing indigenous art in the whole of Australia. Over the years she has developed close and personal relationships with individual artists and their families and friends. She exhibits all forms of artwork and follows a fairly standard practice across the board of a 60/40 split between the gallery and the artist. Beverly has undertaken a highly credible art authentication course run by Melbourne University and she believes that the most common method of proving authentication still lies with expert judgement from qualified individuals who are highly trained and skilled in that particular area/era of artwork. She has close connections with the Queensland government but does not receive any funding from any government sectors. She is on the On-Sale Royalties Committee and believes the current system and legislation is very poor and that the ‘carpetbaggers’ scheme around it. Refer to interview for a detailed example. There is a review of the legislation scheduled for next year and she is hoping there will be a positive outcome. Beverly has some strong opinions about the state of market and the internal politics that have been going on for as long as she can remember. These were some of her points:

- The Aboriginal Art Code was not given enough funding by the Government for proper implementation. She was asked to be on the board but declined the offer as she felt, and still feels that the cause is not what it claims to be and that many hide their poor practices behind it.
- A lot of corruption exists within the market and this is driven by greed and financial gain. This corruption and unethical behaviour is no stranger to indigenous people who are involved in the art dealing and resale side of the market.
- Some Art Centres are better than others as far as their individual standards and treatment of artists. Some actually have very poor conditions and their objectives are

somewhat questionable.

- Pictures and videos of artists are very yesterday and this is not something that would add value to the Aboriginal artwork she sells at the Alcaston, in fact she believes it would achieve the opposite. She thinks that videotaping the process is a crude idea and it is the aesthetics of an artwork that ultimately sell the piece. “Stories don’t sell paintings; stories inspire artists”
- She feels that the buyers she deals with ultimately make their purchase decisions on the aesthetic appearance of the artwork. They want the pieces to live with them in their homes. Of course, size and price are two other key determinants.
- The Gallery has trust from buyers that the work sold there is authentic and Beverly would not do anything to jeopardise the reputation of the gallery. If she is ever in doubt about a piece of artwork, or suspects a collaborative effort has been involved, she simply does not accept it.
- Technological advancements have meant that even remote artists can still achieve success in the larger art market.
- The most valuable buyer markets for the Alcaston Gallery are private collectors as well as institutions, not investors. Approximately 50% of sales are in NSW and 20% internationally. Technology plays a massive part in facilitating both interstate and international sales.
- Education of young indigenous artists is vital. Young artists in today’s modern world are faced with different issues than the generations before them and sometimes these issues can affect their ability to develop creatively.
- Has the view that the Art Centres can be very controlling and have a tendency to lump all artists into the same boat (so to speak) and this is detrimental because no artists are ever the same.
- Freight and services regarding import and export are getting better as far as price and the destinations they can reach. This is an area that has improved immensely as modern technology has progressed.

Colin McKinnon-Dodd of the Mia Mia Gallery Interview Summary

Laura McKinnon

As expected, our meeting with Colin was very informative. The severity of exploitation and fraudulent activity within the Aboriginal art industry was emphasised and the extremities of these problems within the market were made astonishingly clear. As a result, it is important to note, that it was a strategic decision, made by Colin, that this project was to be developed and executed by independent and unbiased contributors. The reason for this is so that the protection of Aboriginal artists and their accompanying artwork would remain absolutely paramount and the control of the developed technology would not be determined by power, price or politics. Colin also emphasised the importance of empowering and involving Aboriginal communities in development and execution of this technology.

In relation to gender-associated cultural sensitivities, it appears that this would not be as great of a concern as first imagined; although, it would be assumed that art buyers would respect the gender confidentialities of the artworks contextual story. It was also discussed that the technology that is to be developed would, most probably, still require the support and input of the art centres and their ability to build and maintain relationships with the Aboriginal communities they are associated to. This is to do with privacy concerns related to sacred cultural events, and dreaming which communities may want to keep on record for historical purposes but not necessarily release for public viewing or to be given to art buyers. This also highlighted the extreme confidentiality and privacy controls that will need to be developed to support this technology.

It was also explained that the capturing of voice and image would not be a concern for end users, although, when it comes to deceased artists, procedures must be put in place to ensure the protection of the associated communities. This would be in the form of warnings for any community members trying to access information on the database so that they do not accidentally stumble upon something they do not wish to see.

And finally, Colin also explained that the parameters of pricing for Aboriginal artwork should depend on whether the artist had been initiated and also the artist's network of dealers that sell their work. He also explained that it was very common for Tourist's and gallery visitors to express great enthusiasm and wonder after learning about the dreaming expressed in the artwork. This information supports and acknowledges the assumption that telling the artworks story is also a value-adding property in the eyes of the buyer.

Interview- Koorie Heritage Trust

Tim Knowles

Koorie Heritage Trust is a not-for-profit organisation established in 1985 which aims to protect, preserve and promote the living culture of Aboriginal people of south-eastern Australia. The Trust's collections also include artworks, rare books, journals and photographs. They introduced us the archival room with a lot of interesting artefacts, such as cloaks, clothing, jewellery, weapons and tools, etc. The possum skin cloak that the Uncle from Koorie Heritage Trust worn made a strong impression on me. This kind of cloak was very common as aboriginal people wore them for protection against the elements. Nowadays, there are only a few known to be in existence. Studying the designs on cloaks was also interesting. According to the Uncle, the motifs on this cloak don't necessarily tell a story, but they are an examination of design work, based on traditional linear motifs. I was also interested in the necklace made of kangaroo teeth. A man wearing a possum skin cloak etched with symbols and a kangaroo tooth necklace displays all the dignified qualities of leadership, and show his deep spiritual connection to the country. The kangaroo teeth can be used for the headband, nose and hair ornaments.

Interview Summary- East Gippsland Aboriginal Arts Corporation (EGAAC)

Quoc-Tan Tran

The visit to the AGACC was an eventful, yet fruitful encounter. After 5 hours of travelling from Geelong to Bairnsdale by car and public transport, Adam and I arrived at the Art Centre to be told that the artists that had been organised to attend the interviews could not make it. After a little confusion, the manager was able to organise a few other people to attend and things started looking up.

We met with a couple of local artists who gave very personal and emotional accounts of their history, their artworks and their feelings of the market. It was clear from their responses that the artists believe they paint not only for the remuneration or prestige, but often as a way of self-expression and it is something that they enjoy doing. One artist remarked that expressing the story is important; however, only some of it needs to be known and other parts need to remain private if the artist chooses that way.

There was some mention about the government's expectations of the community art centres. We got the feeling that there was, broadly speaking, some disdain towards the government's scrutiny and bureaucratic manner of getting things work. Asking the interviewees to fill out ethical clearance forms before we got underway made us feel like we were part of such bureaucracy and it didn't help when one attendee remarked to another *'here, sign these forms, and then they will take your firstborn.'*

The role and importance of the community art centre became increasingly apparent. *'There's nothing else like this place'*, remarked a member of the arts corporation board. Looking from the outside in, it was a community networking hub, a place for workshops, fundraising, facilitation and discussion of aboriginal affairs, as well as a place to create, display and distribute art. It became increasingly clear that the community art centres would have to play a pivotal role in the driving the usage of a smart art system as it was apparent that the artists relied heavily upon the centre for supplies, publicity and as part of a wider community.

The artists warmed to the idea of implementing technology to help express their stories, though we didn't delve too deep into the issues of on-sale royalties, we got the sense that having full ownership and copyright of their artworks was extremely important as the artworks carry much of their personal culture and heritage.

References

- Acker, T. (2008). 'Aboriginal art, it's a complicated thing', *Artlink*, viewed 26 March 2012, <<http://www.artlink.com.au/articles/3144/aboriginal-art-its-a-complicated-thing/>>.
- Anderson, S. (2011). 'Fly-on-the-wall view of Aboriginal affairs', *The Canberra Times*, 27 October 2011.
- Ayres, R. (2007). 'Report on indigenous arts and crafts in Australia', viewed 11 March 2012, <<http://www.artslaw.com.au/articles/entry/report-on-indigenous-arts-and-craft-in-australia/>>.
- Battersby, L. (2012). 'Super Proposal 'could devastate' Aboriginal art', *The Sydney Morning Herald*, 6 July 2010, viewed 11 March 2012. <<http://www.smh.com.au/business/super-proposal-could-devastate-aboriginal-art-20100705-zxol.html>>.
- Buchtman, L. (2000). Digital Songlines: The Use of Modern Communication Technology by an Aboriginal Community in Remote Australia, *Prometheus*, 18(1), 59-74.
- Christie, M. (2007). Fracturing the skeleton of principle: Australian law, Aboriginal Law, and digital technology, *Learning Communities: International Journal of Learning in Social Contexts*, 30-39.
- Christie, M. & Verran, H. (2007). Using/ Designing digital technologies of representation in aboriginal Australian knowledge practices, *Human Technology: Interdisciplinary Journal on Humans in ICT Environments*, Volume 3 (2), May 2007, Finland.
- Circuit, E. (2012). Aboriginal Art goes Digital in Darwin, Thriving in the Desert, 7 August 2011. Viewed 10 March 2012. <<http://thrivinginthedesert.blogspot.com.au/2011/08/aboriginal-art-goes-digital-in-darwin.html>>.
- Connolly, E. (2012). 'More to aboriginal art than connecting the dots', *The Sydney Morning Herald*, 6 March 2012. Viewed 11 March 2012. <<http://www.smh.com.au/entertainment/art-and-design/more-to-aboriginal-art-than-connecting-the-dots-20120305-1ue5o.html>>.
- Foley, D. (2010). 'The function of Social (and Human) Capital as antecedents on Indigenous entrepreneurs networking', *Annals of Tourism Research*, vol. 29, no. 3, p. 631-647 viewed 11 March 2012.
- Furphy, J. (2012). 'The 2011 Australian Art Auction Market', *Australian Art Sales Digest*, viewed 22 April 2012. <http://www.aasd.com.au/ArtMarketReview_2011.cfm>.

Ingram, T. (2007). 'Policy change for indigenous art sales', *The Australian Financial Review*, 5 Dec. 2007, General OneFile.

Johnston, C. (2011). 'Our indigenous Louvre', *The Age*, 28 May.

Kral, I. (2010). *Plugged in: Remote Australian Indigenous Youth and Digital Culture*, Centre for Aboriginal economic policy Research, The Australian National University, Canberra.

Lehn, D., Hindmarsh, P. & Heath, C. (2007). 'Engaging Constable: Revealing Art with New Technology', King's College London, viewed 8 May 2012, <<http://www.takebay.net/data/chi07/docs/p1485.pdf>>.

Morgan, J. (2011). 'A culture crying out for celebration', *The Sydney Morning Herald*, 24 September.

Medicus, (2011). 'Indigenous paintings promote healing for mental health patients', August.

Nathan, D. (2005). Plugging in Indigenous knowledge: connections and innovations, *Australian Aboriginal Studies*, Spring-Fall, 39.

Rintoul, S. (2012). 'Elders' line in the sand on songlines', *The Australian*, 20 May 2012.

Rothwell, N. (2011). 'Art market gets ugly as indigenous bubble bursts', *The Australian*, 31 July.

Rothwell, N. (2011). 'Lost in foreign translation – Western Desert Art: 40 years on', *The Australian*, 30 September.

Schwarzer, M. (2011). *Art & Gadgetry: The future of the museum visit*, Museum News, July/August.

Seabrook, J. (2004). *Consuming Cultures: Globalization and Local Lives*. Oxford: New Internationalist.

Simons, M. (2000). Aboriginal heritage art and moral rights, *Annals of Tourism Research*, Volume 27 issue 2, University of New South Wales, Australia.

Strickland, K. (2007). 'What price indigenous art', *Australian Financial Review*, 27 June 2007. General OneFile.

Taylor, D. & Coleman, L. (2011), Price determinants of Aboriginal art and its role as an alternative asset class, *Journal of Banking & Finance*, Department of Finance, The University of Melbourne, Australia.

Thakur, M. (2010). 'How technology influences art and creativity', *International Business Times*, 7 November.

Turk, A. (2003). Digital Divide Remediation: An Australian Indigenous Community Case Study, *Southern Review: Communication, Politics & Culture*, 36 (1), 48-63.

Verran, H. & Christie M. (2007). Using/designing digital technologies of representation in aboriginal australian knowledge practices, *An Interdisciplinary Journal on Humans in ICT Environments*, 3(2), 214-277.

Verran, H., Christie, M., Anbins-King, B., Van Weeren, T. & Yunupingu, W. (2007). Designing digital knowledge management tools with Aboriginal Australians, *Digital Creativity*, 18 (3), 129-142.

Wilson, A. (2010). 'Aboriginal art dying with desert masters', *The Australian*, 18 September.

Yallamas, L. (2001). Exciting new indigenous art, but at what price?, *Australasian Business Intelligence*, 26 Aug, General OneFile.